

Feasibility of using Oxford Nanopore Technology for population genomics in *Fagus sylvatica*: A pilot study

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Keywords: long-read sequencing, pool sequencing (pool-seq), European beech, epigenetic markers, structural variants (SVs), single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs)

Abstract

We conducted a pilot study to evaluate the feasibility of using Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) to analyze genetic variation among cohorts of European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) individuals in the context of a long-term monitoring program. Oxford Nanopore guarantees support of reference chemistry for long-term studies, and ONT offers potential to recover structural and epigenetic variants as well as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). However, population genomics requires scalable approaches. We extracted DNA from dormant leaf buds of 18 adult trees and sequenced these either with individual barcodes, or as a single pool (ca. equimolar pooling) with the aim of saving costs. The comparison of individually barcoded versus pooled samples was conducted in duplicate (two replicate flow cells) using a PromethION. Results were generally reproducible across flow cells, but numbers of reads across individually barcoded samples varied, likely due to differences in DNA intactness or small differences in size distribution that may have been further biased during library preparation. Furthermore, a disproportionately low number of sequencing reads was obtained for the pooled sample. Although seemingly a cost-saving measure, we do not recommend sample pooling, as ensuring equal representation requires detailed, often cost-intensive characterization of samples prior to pooling, making low-coverage sequencing of individual samples often the more feasible option. The low-coverage data we obtained yielded interpretable SNP variation (which, however, remains more accurate using short-read sequencing techniques), but failed to yield reproducible data on epigenetic and structural variants. In conclusion, scaling ONT to population genomics would benefit from the development of more cost-effective methods to ensure even representation across samples and to obtain more reproducible information on variants, especially structural and epigenetic variants, with lower sequencing coverage.

Introduction

The advancement of genomic technologies has enabled genome-wide analysis of genetic variation at lower cost and higher resolution, allowing new questions to be addressed across medicine, biology, ecology, and evolution. Population genomics has become a central approach in understanding local adaptation, demographic history, and conservation genetics (Luikart et al., 2003). To date, population-level sequencing efforts have been dominated by short-read sequencing technologies, such as those offered by Illumina. These enable high-throughput, low-coverage, and cost-effective approaches, including (low-coverage) individual and pooled sequencing (pool-seq) (Lou et al., 2021; Schlötterer et al., 2014).

However, short-read sequencing has intrinsic limitations: it struggles to resolve complex structural variants (SVs) and map repetitive genomic regions (Amarasinghe et al., 2020), and the most commonly used provider, Illumina, does not guarantee reference techniques for long-term studies. Third-generation long-read technologies—such as Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) and Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT)—have emerged as powerful alternatives by producing reads that span kilobases, and, in the case of ONT, by enabling direct detection of base modifications from native DNA (Jain et al., 2018; Simpson et al., 2017; Vaillancourt and Buell, 2019) as well as providing modular platforms that can be used with a variety of chemistries and maintaining specific reference chemistries to support comparability in long-term studies. ONT has attracted particular interest due to its portability and ability to deliver ultra-long reads in real time.

Despite its potential, the application of ONT in population genomics remains limited, particularly in plants. Most current ONT applications in plant genomics have focused on producing *de novo* genome assemblies using high-quality DNA from single individuals (Michael et al., 2018). Long-read sequencing of multiple individuals, particularly using pooled strategies, is technically challenging. ONT requires high-molecular-weight DNA that is sufficiently pure and intact (Dumschott et al., 2020; Russo et al., 2022). DNA of sufficient quality can require more effort to obtain, especially in plant systems due to rigid cell walls and the presence of diverse secondary metabolites (Schmidt et al., 2017). ONT is sensitive to variation in sample quality, which can result in biased sequencing depth, underrepresentation of samples, and reduced variant detection accuracy (De Coster et al., 2021). Furthermore, the error rate remains higher relative to Illumina short reads, complicating downstream analyses when sequencing at low coverage, a common compromise in population-scale projects.

In this technical note, we present a pilot study evaluating the feasibility of using Oxford Nanopore sequencing in a population genomics context for the European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) and given a cost ceiling. European beech is among the most ecologically and economically important forest tree species in Central Europe and is increasingly threatened by climate change, particularly by severe drought events such as that observed in 2018 (Leuschner, 2020). This study aims to evaluate whether the pilot approach can be scaled into a long-term genetic monitoring program for beech forests in Switzerland and if not, what changes would be required.

The European beech genome size is 542 Mb with 12 chromosomes and high heterozygosity (Milesi et al., 2024; Mishra et al., 2022). In this study we targeted low coverage (<5×) sequencing, as is common in population genomics (Lou et al., 2021). We

compared the results from pooled (approximately equimolar) and individually barcoded DNA samples, evaluating their performance in capturing allele frequencies, structural variants, and epigenetic modifications with comparison to the Bhaga reference genome (available on NCBI: GCA_907173295.1). Our findings indicate that despite ONT's attractive features, practical limitations such as stringent sample quality requirements and possible unequal sequencing representation make pooling approaches difficult to interpret and reduce the utility of low-coverage sequencing for population genomic inference. These results offer valuable guidance for the development of population-scale plant genomic techniques using ONT as a sequencing platform.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection

Samples were harvested in February 2024 from top-of-canopy branches of adult trees using a remotely piloted aircraft system (RPAS) (DJI Matrice 600, DJI, Beijing, China) coupled with a treetop sampler (DeLeaves, Outreach Robotics, Sherbrooke, Quebec, Canada). The plot is located in Rafz, Switzerland and is part of an inter-cantonal long-term forest monitoring program (Braun et al., 2021).

The bud samples were stored in a teabag on silica gel and kept outdoors under winter temperatures until they were transported to the lab and stored at 4 °C until further processing, a common practice in ecological genetic studies conducted in remote field locations. However, we note that storage on silica gel may affect DNA quality to an extent that is more likely to affect long- than short-read sequencing; see discussion.

DNA extraction and library preparation for Oxford Nanopore sequencing

DNA was extracted from +/- 20 mg inner tissue of 20 dormant beech leaf buds (step 1a of the DNA extraction and libraryprep QC file in the Zenodo repository). Scales were removed and inner tissue was placed into SafeLock microcentrifuge tubes containing two 4 mm metal beads and frozen at -20 °C. Tissue was ground by first snap-freezing tubes containing samples by dipping the lower part, as well as the rack holding the tubes, in liquid N₂, and then milling for 120 s at 23 Hz using a TissueLyser II (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Long milling can affect DNA quality and length, but tissue homogenization and cell disruption is essential for DNA yield and sample representativeness. We made sure to always have the samples frozen by dipping the tubes with samples in liquid N₂ after every 30 s of grinding.

DNA was extracted from the resulting fine, homogeneous powder using a modified version of the Norgen Biotek Plant/Fungi DNA Isolation kit (Norgen Biotek, Thorold, Ontario, Canada), to obtain high-quality, high-molecular weight DNA with reduced RNA contamination and improved lysis efficiency, yield and purity (Czyż et al., 2025; Schmid et al., 2024). Quality control was performed using agarose gel electrophoresis, a microvolume UV spectrophotometer (Nanodrop) and fluorometer (QuBit) (Step 1b). While some samples produced a single broad band of intact genomic DNA, other samples produced a range of genomic DNA fragments from ca. 3 kbp to >20 kbp. To obtain a size distribution of similar length across samples, and given that such mid-length fragments are commonly understood to be more efficiently sequenced by

ONT, the intact DNA was sheared using a bead-beating method on those samples with highest molecular weight. For this, two 3 mm metal beads were added to 1.5 mL tubes (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany), and DNA was dissolved in molecular-grade water to a final concentration of 700 ng in 60 μ L; samples were sheared in a TissueLyser II by shaking at 30 Hz for 10 s, rotating 180°, and shaken again for 10 s. The DNA was transferred by pipetting to a PCR strip, where the size selection was performed using AMPure XP beads on all samples (Step 2). We followed an internal protocol that is according to a protocol provided on GitHub (repseqio) with the following specifications: on average, 18.45 μ L of AmPure XP beads were used to receive a 0.41 \times ratio on a DNA volume of 41 - 48 μ L. We did not mix by pipetting, but by agitating the tubes by snapping with the fingers to reduce shearing. We used 80% Ethanol for the washing steps and 42.5 μ L of molecular water to elute and incubate at room temperature for 2 min. We were able to transfer 40 μ L of the size-selected DNA at the end. The concentration was measured using the QuBit fluorometer and for samples 1_A_1 - 1_A_11, 15, 17 and 19 the microvolume spectrophotometer (Nanodrop) was additionally used to judge purity. Extracted, sheared, and size-selected DNA from samples 1_A_5, 6, 7, 17 and 19 did not or just meet our criteria for amount (concentration below 30 ng/ μ L) and quality (260/230 ratio under 1.8) and we repeated DNA extraction and size selection, and named the samples 1_A_ Xb (step 3).

Prior to this study, the functionality and performance of the size selection and shearing was tested with test samples, see TapeStation report (Zenodo repository) where all peaks were around 10kbp (outliers would have to be excluded for further sample processing).

All samples were stored at 4 °C overnight, kept on ice during handling, or frozen at -20 °C for storage periods exceeding four days.

Two samples (1_A_17b and 1_A_19b) still did not meet the required quality and length and were removed from the study. Their 260/230 ratios were 1.43 and 1.35, DNA concentration 7.07 ng/ μ L and 17.6 ng/ μ L, and almost no DNA appeared on the gel image (see gel image step 3). Aliquots of 100 ng DNA from the other 18 size-normalized samples of the cohort used for this pilot study were mixed in equal mass, assuming that, due to the standardized size profile, the samples are equimolar within the pool (see volume concentration table in the Zenodo repository).

Figure 1: Illustration of the experimental design. Individual samples were collected from multiple trees and barcoded (barcodes 1–18), while barcode 19 represents a pooled mixture of individuals. After library preparation, two replicate libraries were sequenced on separate PromethION flow cells. Created in BioRender. Guerra, T. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/2p3jqrd>.

Library preparation and native barcoding of samples were conducted according to the ONT PromethION protocol (“Ligation sequencing gDNA - Native Barcoding Kit 24 V14 (SQK-NBD114.24),” n.d.) up to the priming step. Samples with volume over 11uL were placed in a vacuum concentrator for 5-7 min. The individuals were each given a native barcode (numbers 1-18), as was the pool, which was given barcode number 19. The individual samples to be analysed were processed with a quantity of 400 ng of DNA each, while the pool was processed with a quantity of 1000 ng for these first steps of library preparation.

The individually barcoded samples were then pooled equimolar based on the laboratory quantification of double-stranded DNA and size distribution (Step 5), and a purification step was performed according to the protocol. Finally, the two pools were mixed to 50% each by DNA amount (Step 6), and the rest of the library preparation, the ligation of the adapter, was completed. Two such replicate libraries were made and a final quality control was performed with an Agilent TapeStation (Step 7). From the final library, 20 fmol was loaded onto the PromethION flow cell to allow duplex basecalling with the aim of obtaining higher accuracy. Duplex basecalling is the reading of both strands and allows rates of up to Q30+, compared to simplex basecalling. The difference between simplex and duplex basecalling is determined when loading the flow cell: 35-50 fmol of library is required for simplex, whereas for duplex it is 10-20 fmol, with a lower yield expected as a trade-off (information from Kit 14 sequencing and duplex basecalling, Legacy document).

Oxford Nanopore sequencing

One final QC was obtained at FGCZ with the Femto Pulse (report in the Zenodo repository) before technicians at their laboratory loaded the library onto two flow cells. Whole-genome sequencing of the two sets of samples (individually barcoded, and mixed pool with a single barcode) was performed using an ONT PromethION_24 instrument with two PromethION Flow Cell R10.4.1 for 96 hours at the Functional Genomics Center Zurich (FGCZ). To test reproducibility of the sequencing procedure, two flow cells were used after loading with replicated libraries.

Bioinformatic analyses

Data preprocessing and downstream analysis were performed with a custom-made bioinformatics pipeline using Snakemake workflow manager (Mölder et al., 2021) and conda environments on the Science Cluster of the University of Zurich. Details on each step are provided below, and see the data, scripts, code in the Zenodo repository for this study.

Data preprocessing

Two different sequence datasets were obtained from PromethION raw data output. These two datasets were generated using “simplex” or “duplex” basecalling. Simplex basecalling from raw data was performed by the FGCZ using Guppy basecaller (v4.3.0 SUP, 2024 Oxford Nanopore Technologies). Modified basecalling was performed for 5mC and 5hmC modified bases. In this report, only the “simplex” dataset was used for modified basecalling.

Duplex basecalling was performed using Dorado (v0.7.2, 2024 Oxford Nanopore Technologies PLC) with the same method and model used for the simplex basecalling.

The next preprocessing steps used basecalled read data from the duplex basecalling process, combined with reads from the simplex basecalling process (Appendix 1, Fig. S1). Read adapters were removed using Porechop v0.2.4 with default parameters (Wick, 2025a). Reads were trimmed using Filtrlong v0.2.1 with a minimum length of 1,000 bases and a minimum base quality of 70, *i.e.*, retaining reads with a mean percent identity (implemented from 0 to 100) above 70 (Wick, 2025b). Reads were mapped to the *Fagus sylvatica* reference genome available on NCBI: GCA_907173295.1 (Mishra et al., 2022) using minimap2 v2.28-r1209 default parameters for Oxford nanopore reads mapping (Li, 2025).

Downstream analysis

Alignment quality assessment, including mean whole-genome coverage, was calculated using Cramino v0.14.5 (De Coster and Rademakers, 2023). Structural variants (SVs, *i.e.*, insertions and deletions) were detected using Sniffles2 v2.4 with default parameters (Smolka et al., 2024). A hard filtering on structural variant breakpoints was applied, and only structural variants with a breakpoint length of 0 were kept. Single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were detected per individual barcode using Clair3 with the rerio model. The output of individual barcode SNPs detection was restricted to the 12 chromosome-scale scaffolds and jointly genotyped using GLNexus. The resulting multi-sample VCF was then filtered with bcftools to retain only biallelic SNPs. Allele frequencies were estimated using Gredalf v0.5.2 with a minimum mapping and base quality threshold of 30 (Czech et al., 2024). Epigenetic modification

analysis was performed using modkit v0.4.1 with default parameters (“nanoporetech/modkit,” 2025).

Results

The output obtained from the two flow cells is compared for the downstream analysis presented below. For an overview of the sequencing output, please see Table 1.

Table 1: Sequencing data output for the two flow cells used in this study. For more detail, see the corresponding sequencing reports in the Zenodo repository for this publication.

Flow cell	Estimated Bases	Reads Generated	Estimated N50
ID PAW43845 (flow cell 1)	59.42 Gb	19.27 M	4.34 kb
ID PAW37894 (flow cell 2)	62.23 Gb	20.74 M	4.44 kb

Allele frequency estimation

We studied the output of the two flow cells that were loaded with replicate libraries. We observed that duplex reads accounted for <1% of the total reads sequenced (Fig. S1). Then, we assessed the whole-genome sequencing mean coverage per barcode after alignment to the reference genome obtained by Cramino. As expected, there was consistency between flow cell 1 and flow cell 2 regarding the total sequencing depth of each barcode (Fig. 2). However, the distribution was not even among the 18 individual barcodes, with coverage ranging from 0.65 \times to 6.55 \times . We observed that the percentage of the pool was much lower than expected (50%), as the individuals and the pool of individuals were loaded in equimolar amounts, *i.e.*, 50% of the total moles loaded onto the flow cell comprised the pooled sample and 50% comprised the individually barcoded samples.

Despite the variation in genome-wide coverage among barcodes, we proceeded to estimate allele frequencies using Gredalf. To facilitate interpretation across the large number of sites, allele frequencies were summarized using a binning approach rather than visualizing all individual observations. The depth-weighted average alternative allele frequency from individually barcoded samples (barcodes 01–18) was grouped into bins (width = 0.02) and compared to the mean allele frequency estimated from the pooled sample (barcode 19) within each bin (Fig. 3). Across both flow cells, the mean pooled allele frequency increased approximately linearly with the binned individual-based estimates and broadly followed the expected 1:1 relationship. Summary statistics were consistent between the two flow cells (flow cell 1: $R^2 = 0.599$, Pearson $r = 0.774$, Spearman $\rho = 0.684$, RMSE = 0.199; flow cell 2: $R^2 = 0.589$, Pearson $r = 0.768$, Spearman $\rho = 0.679$, RMSE = 0.203; Appendix 2: Table S1). However, the spread of values within bins remained substantial, as reflected by the wide 10th–90th percentile ranges,

indicating considerable variability in pooled allele frequency estimates at the site level. To illustrate the underlying distribution of individual sites, hexbin density plots of all observations are provided in Appendix 3: Fig. S2.

At lower sequencing depths, allele frequency estimates showed greater deviation between the pooled and individually barcoded samples (Fig. 4). Here, sequencing depth refers to the site-level total depth used for the allele-frequency comparison, not the genome-wide average barcode coverage shown in Figure 2. Mean absolute deviation was highest at low coverage and decreased steadily with increasing depth. At higher sequencing depths, deviations were substantially reduced, indicating more consistent allele frequency estimates between the pooled and individual samples. This pattern was consistent across both flow cells. Mean signed deviation remained close to zero across sequencing-depth bins, suggesting that the observed pattern primarily reflects variability in the magnitude of deviation rather than a strong systematic bias.

Figure 2: Whole-genome sequencing mean coverage (y-axis) per barcode (x-axis) for flow cell 1 (blue) and flow cell 2 (orange). barcodes 1-18 are the individually barcoded samples while barcode 19 is the mixed pool.

Figure 3: Binned comparison of allele frequency estimates between individually barcoded samples and the pooled sample. The depth-weighted average alternative allele frequency estimated from individually barcoded samples (barcodes 01–18) was grouped into bins of width 0.02. For each bin, the mean alternative allele frequency in the pooled sample (barcode 19) is shown. Point size reflects the number of sites per bin, and vertical error bars indicate the 10th–90th percentile range of pooled-sample allele frequencies within each bin. The dashed red line represents the expected 1:1 relationship.

Figure 4: Relationship between sequencing depth and allele frequency deviation. Mean absolute deviation between the pooled sample (barcode 19) and the depth-weighted average allele frequency from individually barcoded samples (barcodes 01–18) is shown as a function of sequencing depth. Points represent mean values within depth bins, and point size reflects the number of sites per bin.

SNP calling

In total, 17,767,779 biallelic SNPs were called across the 12 chromosome-scale scaffolds after variant calling with Clair 3, joint genotyping with GLNexus, and filtering with bcftools. The genotypes are coded as -1 (not called), 0 (homozygous reference), 1 (heterozygous), and 2 (homozygous alternative). The genotype composition was highly consistent between the two replicate flow cells (Fig. 5). This consistency is confirmed by the quantitative estimates of observed heterozygosity (H_o). Across the 18 individual samples, the average H_o was 0.126 ± 0.078 (mean \pm s.d.) for flow cell 1 and 0.127 ± 0.077 for flow cell 2. As expected, the pooled sample (barcode 19) displayed a higher H_o (0.344 for flow cell 1 and 0.338 for flow cell 2), numerically confirming the increased heterogeneity introduced by pooling. Across the 18 individual barcodes, the average missing rate was $9.8 \pm 0.6\%$ in flow cell 1 and $9.6 \pm 0.6\%$ in flow cell 2. For barcode 19, the missing rates were 19.7% and 19.4% in flow cell 1 and flow cell 2, respectively.

Figure 5: Proportion of genotype categories for each barcode across two replicate flow cells. Genotypes were coded as -1 (not called), 0 (homozygous reference), 1 (heterozygous), and 2 (homozygous alternative).

Structural variants

We compared structural variants between barcodes among the two flow cells using Sniffles2. We compared whether we obtained the same number of calls and identical structural variant call positions along chromosome 1 of the beech genome across the flow cells. We compared two individuals with low coverage (mean = 1.35) versus high coverage (mean = 5) in our dataset (barcode 01, low coverage, and barcode 04, high coverage; Fig. 2).

For both individuals, we observed a higher number of deletion calls than other categories, followed by insertions, with a higher number of total calls for barcode 04 (Fig. 6). Then, we compared whether identical structural variant calls were obtained across flow cells for both individuals. For barcode 01, we observed 36% identical structural variant calls between flow cells, compared to 63% for barcode 04. The difference in the number of calls and the difference in identical shared base positions might be influenced by observed total depth sequencing differences among barcodes (Fig. 2). A heatmap of all structural variants called on all chromosomes 1-12 for all barcodes is in the supplementary Zenodo repository.

Figure 6: Number of structural variant calls along chromosome 1 (y-axis) of two individuals with different depths of coverage (left, barcode 01, lower coverage and right, barcode 04, higher coverage, see Fig. 1) for flow cell 1 (blue) and flow cell 2 (orange). The x-axis indicates the different types of structural variants: BND (Independent breakend), DE (Deletion), DUP (Duplication), INS (Insertion), and INV (Inversion).

Barcode 01

Barcode 04

Figure 7: Number of shared structural variant call base positions along chromosome 1. Left, barcode 01, lower coverage and right, barcode 04, higher coverage (see Fig. 2). Note difference in y-axis scale.

Epigenetic variants

Data on epigenetic modifications (5mC and 5hmC) were acquired during sequencing. In this study, only the reproducibility of the measurements between individual-level epigenetic measurements across flow cells will be presented.

We compared epigenetic modification calls along chromosome 1 of the beech genome for the same individuals studied above, barcoded as barcode 01 (lower coverage) and barcode 04 (higher coverage, see Fig. 2) across the two flow cells. First, we observed that 5mC modifications mainly represent epigenetic modification calls. Second, we observed a higher number of calls for barcode 04 than for barcode 01 (Fig. 7). Finally, as for structural variant calling, we compared whether identical base positions with epigenetic modification calls were identified across flow cells for both individuals. For barcode 01, we observed that 30% of base positions are shared across flow cells. In comparison, for barcode 04, we observed 60% of shared base positions (Fig. 8). These differences are consistent with those observed for structural variants on chromosome 1 and are thought to be due to the observed total depth of sequencing differences between these barcodes (Fig. 2). A heatmap of all epigenetic 5mC modifications called on all chromosomes 1-12 for all barcodes is in the supplementary Zenodo repository.

Figure 8: Number of epigenetic modification calls (y-axis) of two individuals (left, barcode 01, lower coverage and right, barcode 04, higher coverage, see Fig. 1) for flow cell 1 (blue) and flow cell 2 (orange). The x-axis shows the two types of epigenetic modification calls.

Barcode 01

Barcode 04

Figure 9: Number of shared base positions along chromosome 1 with epigenetic modification calls. Left, barcode 01, lower coverage and right, barcode 04, higher coverage (see Fig. 1). Note difference in y-axis scale.

Summary and discussion of the results

Sequencing depth and evenness

We observed sequencing depth variation and differences in read numbers sequenced across individuals, which likely led to accuracy differences in the downstream analyses, especially structural variant calling and epigenetic modification detection. Despite these variations, we observed reproducibility of patterns between the two flow cells that each received an identical mixture of prepared DNA extracts. In particular, differences among samples were reproducible between the two flow cells. This indicates that these differences were caused by differences in sample quality and perhaps associated small differences in molarity that may have been amplified during library preparation (“Oxford Nanopore Technology - Research Technology Support Facility”). Sample quality is known to be especially important for long-read sequencing techniques (De Coster et al., 2021), including Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT), which uses the native (extracted) DNA molecules for sequencing. We therefore did not extend the comparison of individually barcoded individuals to the pool of these individuals (barcode 19 in our study). The uneven sequencing read depths among individuals (barcodes 01-18), which composed the pool barcode 19, might be reflected within, leading to difficulties in downstream analysis interpretations (Gautier et al., 2013; Schlötterer et al., 2014). This is indicated by the higher level of heterozygosity in the pool barcode 19. Nevertheless, pooled sequencing approaches can provide reliable estimates of population genetic parameters when appropriate sampling and analytical strategies are applied, although unequal sequencing coverage across libraries remains a major source of potential bias (Chen et al., 2016).

Even if samples have been carefully adjusted to achieve equimolarity before pooling, library preparation can introduce selectivity. Therefore, it is necessary to verify barcode distribution after barcoding individual samples, using, for example, a Flongle run or a short (one-hour) run on the Promethlon flow cell, and use these data to adjust the pooling accordingly. As a result, if pooled sequencing is intended to reduce costs (which is usually the main reason), the pooling must be done at the tissue level before extraction. This will likely also produce biases because DNA may not be extracted at equal efficiency and in equal quality from all of the different samples used to make the pooled tissue sample; however, these biases can no longer be assessed, saving costs that would otherwise be incurred by the assessment of individual samples prior to the final pooling. Once it is desirable to extract individual samples, pooling after extraction is no longer cost-effective in most cases, especially if it is important to eliminate between-sample differences in the pool (which is usually the case).

In this study, we aimed to test a cost-effective and scalable approach that could have costs comparable to short-read sequencing at similar depth. Thus, not only did we not use the low-coverage sequence information from individually barcoded samples to adjust their representation in a pooled sample, we also did not use high-resolution size-normalization techniques (e.g., BluePippin), nor did we use high size-resolution methods (e.g., Agilent TapeStation) to confirm the normalized size distribution of every sample prior to pooling, given that an initial trial had shown reproducible size ranges in size-normalized samples. Although these measures should improve the evenness of sequencing depth across samples, they are not scalable and would have added more labor and at least EUR 33.- to the cost of each individual sample (Dumschott et al., 2020). Thus, all of these good-practice measures that become especially important when pooling samples reduce the potential cost savings. Rather, because we had a practical limit on budget per sample, we used agarose gel electrophoresis to check the size distribution across all samples, alongside spectrometry and fluorometry to judge sample purity and concentration.

In summary, consistent with the work by Lou and colleagues (2021)—who, however, focused on short-read sequencing—our study indicates that a better data-to-cost ratio is obtained by barcoding individual samples and conducting low-coverage sequencing rather than pooling samples. However, the potential additional information that can be obtained from long-read sequencing is greatly reduced with low coverage.

Sample preparation, DNA quality, and scalability

DNA extraction from plant tissues remains challenging not only due to structural barriers such as rigid cell walls, but also because secondary metabolites, particularly polysaccharides and phenolic compounds are difficult to remove and tend to co-precipitate with DNA (Dumschott et al., 2020). Tissue handling and sampling storage was performed to our best knowledge. The samples were consistently stored on ice, in a refrigerator or in a freezer. In addition, tissue homogenization was performed under frozen conditions using liquid N₂, which helps preserve DNA integrity by limiting nuclease activity (Schenk et al., 2023).

Although all samples used in our study were processed to have a nearly identical measured DNA size distribution and had high quality as measured using standard

low-cost protocols (electrophoresis, Qubit, and DeNovix), the results indicate that our DNA extraction procedures likely should be changed from a spin-column kit to a protocol with additional and gentler purification steps. Such protocols that are generally recommended for long-read sequencing are lower-yield and more labor-intensive and are thus also less scalable. While this result is not surprising based on common recommendations, our aim in this study was to test quantitative outputs with high-quality DNA as obtained using a more scalable extraction approach.

The specific considerations for sample size and quality for sequencing are, to some extent, particular to individual types of samples and methods. Because the majority of expertise with ONT has been developed using human and microbial (medical) samples (De Meulenaere et al., 2023), fewer studies have developed practical recommendations for plant samples; and these generally aimed at very long reads to support genome assembly rather than at scalable methods for surveying genomic diversity (Aury et al., 2022; Canaguier et al., 2021; van Rengs et al., 2022). Some details remain to be developed, especially when trying (as here) to implement ONT for a population genomics approach. As is also the case for short-read sequencing, pooling of independently extracted samples entails substantial additional work, as discussed above. To our knowledge, no population genomics protocol using ONT has yet been published.

Use of ONT in plant population genomics

Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) is widely used for plant genome and organelle sequencing, and recently, there are a few first examples of population-level applications in plants. However, most work remains focused on building reference genomes and benchmarking methods for crops and the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*. For example, a population-scale SV study in soybean used ONT long reads (~12× coverage) for 17 cultivars to discover structural variants, then genotyped these SVs in a population of 102 cultivars using Illumina data (Lemay et al., 2021). Benchmarking of ONT-based SV detection pipelines was done in rapeseed, tomato, maize, and soybean across coverages typical for resequencing (5–20×) to guide ONT-based re-sequencing and SV discovery in crop genomes (Yildiz et al., 2023). A tool and R package (sounDMR) was developed specifically for population epigenomics in plants using ONT methylation calls, demonstrated on a population of *Arabidopsis* treated with a demethylating agent to identify regions of high epigenetic variability between individuals (Colicchio et al., 2023). A recent review reports ONT sequencing has been used to sequence >100 plant mitochondrial and ~80 chloroplast genomes (Sawicki et al., 2024), which are much easier to acquire at high coverage with less effort due to their small size and abundant copy numbers in plant cells. Tools such as NanoPack2 have also been developed to analyze long-read data at population scales (De Coster and Rademakers, 2023). Overall, as a relatively low-cost and low-barrier technology, the potential of ONT for plant population genomics is recognized (Dumschott et al., 2020; Ferguson et al., 2022; Pucker et al., 2022). However, barriers remain to handling field samples and wild, heterozygous, non-model organisms at scale. The current advantages of ONT are likely greatest for studies focused specifically on structural variants, in which cases ONT sequencing may be employed for a subset of samples and used to guide design or interpretation of short-read sequencing; or when there is a focus on epigenetic variants.

Conclusions

Finally, our results indicate that a higher sequencing depth would be required for beech individuals to be able to correctly study structural variants (Jiang et al., 2021) and epigenetic modifications: two of the main advantages of using long-read sequencing. We observed an accuracy increase with a coverage of 5x, suggesting that a mean coverage of 10x may be sufficient to detect structural variants and epigenetic modifications for beech individuals. We note that the financial outlay required for library preparation and sequencing of individual samples with Illumina WGS low-coverage is still approximately one-third of that for ONT as of the time of writing. Nevertheless, the guarantee by ONT to maintain specific chemistries over the long-term is a potential advantage for time series and monitoring studies and, to our knowledge, is not yet an option provided by short-read sequencing techniques. We also note that short-read sequencing and associated sample preparation protocols introduce bias in sequencing output that may be less apparent than the biases we were able to quantify in this test dataset with native DNA sequencing using ONT.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Fig. S1 Reads number per basecalling mode across flow cells.

Figure S1: Number of “simplex” and “duplex” basecalled reads across the barcode for two flow cells. The left panel corresponds to the 1st flow cell and the right panel to the 2nd flow cell. Each bar corresponds to the total number of reads sequenced. Blue represents the simplex basecalling number of reads, and red represents the duplex basecalling number of reads.

Appendix 2: Table S1 Summary statistics between the two flow cells

Table S1: Summary statistics for the comparison of allele frequency estimates between individually barcoded samples and the pooled sample for each flow cell.

Flow cell	Number of sites	R ²	Pearson r	Spearman ρ	RMS E	Mean absolute deviation
1	17,639,056	0.599	0.774	0.684	0.199	0.133

2	17,075,648	0.5 89	0.768	0.679	3	0.20	0.135
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Appendix 3: Fig. S2 Underlying distribution of individuals.

Figure S2: Hexbin density plots showing the relationship between the depth-weighted average alternative allele frequency from individually barcoded samples (barcodes 01–18) and the allele frequency estimated from the pooled sample (barcode 19) for all sites. Color intensity reflects the number of sites per hexagonal bin (log-scaled). The dashed red line indicates the expected 1:1 relationship. Results are shown separately for the two flow cells.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful for expert support from the Amt für Wald und Wild beider Basel and the guidance of Ueli Meier, the expert support of the Institute for Angewandte Pflanzenbiologie and the guidance of Simon Tresch and Sabine Braun, the expert support of the Genetic Diversity Center at the ETH Zurich and the guidance of Aria Maya Minder Pfyl, Silvia Kobel and Niklaus Zemp, the guidance of Anna Bratus-Neuenschwander and Weihong Qi and the support of the Functional Genomic Center, Prof. Dr. Miriam Langer from Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz for her support, and the support of the Spatial Genetics group, especially help from Jeremiah Huggel, Sofia van Moorsel, Marharyta Smohunova, and alumna Tis Voortman, at the University of Zurich for a larger related sample collection campaign from which these samples for testing were derived. We acknowledge the use of Consensus to support the literature review of studies using ONT in applications related to plant population genomics (Discussion) and of DeepL Writing and Chat GPT to support phrasing.

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

Raw sequence data are available on ENA under Project No: PRJEB107111 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB107111>). Codes, DNA extraction and

library preparation quality control, TapeStation report, Femto Pulse and sequencing report, heatmap of structural variants and epigenetics for all barcodes and ReadMe files are available on Zenodo, DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/20427191>. Pod5 Oxford Nanopore native data will be provided upon request to the senior author.

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

Funding

This study has been funded by the Amt für Wald beider Basel, the NOMIS Foundation project “Remotely Sensing Ecological Genomics” to PI M. E. Schaepman (M. C. Schuman is Co-Investigator), and the University of Zurich.

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